

octomaculata or *P. fuscipes*. Except for the spider, no predator was cannibalistic. When 1 spider was caged with 10 *C. lividipennis* and 10 WBPH, *C. lividipennis* had 41% mortality and WBPH only 27%.

We also studied the feeding activity of the predators on WBPH. *L. pseudoannulata* ate the most (5.9) WBPH per day (see table). Feeding rate of the other predators ranged from 1.4 to 2.4 WBPH per day.

These laboratory studies were under conditions that may differ from those in the field, and only adult stages were tested. In the field, it is likely that intraspecific and interspecific predation also occurs at immature stages. *J*

Effect of custard apple oil, neem Oil, and neem cake on green leafhopper (GLH) population and on tungro (RTV) infection

R. C. Saxena, principal research scientist, International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology, Nairobi, Kenya, and entomologist, IRRI; and H. D. Justo, Jr., research assistant, IRRI

In laboratory studies at IRRI, mixtures of seed oils of custard apple *Annona squamosa* L. and neem *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss were significantly more effective in reducing GLH survival and its transmission of RTV than spray application of individual oils.

In field trials, we sprayed a 1:4 (vol:vol) mixture of custard apple and neem seed oils at 50% concentration on RTV-susceptible IR42 plants. The mixture was applied with an ultralow-volume applicator at weekly intervals from seedling to maximum tillering stages at 8 litres/ha. A 3:10 (weight:weight) neem cake-urea mixture also was applied at 60, 30, and 30 kg N/ha at seedling stage, maximum tillering, and panicle initiation. The treated control was sprayed with BPMC at 0.75 kg ai/ha and the untreated control with the emulsifier at weekly intervals from seedling to maximum tillering.

For three consecutive croppings in 1984-85, IR42 treated with the oil mixture alone or in combination with neem cake + urea had relatively low GLH populations, consistently low RTV infection, and high yields (Fig. 1). At 9% RTV infection in Jun-Oct 1985, plants with the oil mixture alone or with neem cake + urea had significantly less RTV infection than the untreated control, but yields were not significantly different.

At \approx 50% RTV infection in Nov 1984-Mar 1985, test plants yielded significantly higher and had markedly

1. Comparison of yield and RTV infection in field plots planted to RTV-susceptible IR42 and treated with either custard apple oil and neem oil (CAO:NO), neem cake + urea (NCU), their combination (CAO:NO and NCU), BPMC, or a detergent-water solution (control). Average of 4 replications. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. IRRI, 1984-85.

2. Correlation between RTV and yield for the Nov 1984-Mar 1985 crop, IRRI.

lower RTV infection when they received the oil mixture alone or neem cake + urea than the insecticide-treated and the untreated controls.

The positive correlation between RTV infection and yield (Fig. 2) during this cropping period indicates that the level

of RTV infection was the major yield determinant and that either the oil mixture alone or oil + neem cake + urea effectively controlled the vector and the disease. Neem cake + urea alone was ineffective. *J*

Activation of prophenol oxidase enzyme by brown planthopper (BPH) in response to insecticide

T. Thangaraj, R. Jeyaraj, C. A. Vasuki, and M. Aruchami, Zoological Research Department, Kongunadu Arts and Science College, Coimbatore 641029, Tamil Nadu, India

It has been proposed that the prophenol oxidase activation system of insects recognizes pathogens such as bacteria and fungi because it is activated by the lipopolysaccharide from bacteria and B-1, 3 glucan from fungus cell walls.